

Humanitarian discourse as racism disclaimer: The representation of Roma in Swedish press

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Abstract

Roma communities remain Europe's most marginalized and disadvantaged population, facing increasing discrimination, especially after the 2015 refugee crisis. European media often portrays them as criminals or anti-social, furthering misunderstanding and social exclusion. This article examines Swedish news media's representation of Roma, which, at a surface level, appears much less negative. Using Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis, we analyze two Swedish newspapers' coverage of the controversial law which sought to criminalize begging, which targeted Eastern European Roma migrants. Our findings reveal that 'Swedish exceptionalism'—a discourse of human rights, equality, colorblindness, characterized by limited racial literacy—serves to obscure and act as a disclaimer for anti-Roma sentiment and government actions which in fact resemble those criticized in other EU countries.

Keywords: anti-Roma racism, colorblind racism, multimodal critical discourse analysis, Swedish exceptionalism, Swedish media

Introduction

Research has shown that news coverage of the Roma in European media has consistently represented them as a problem to be solved: as backward, criminal, immoral, a threat to social order, a drain on resources and as extremely 'other' (Breazu & McGarry 2023; Catalano & Fielder 2018; Tremlett et al. 2017). Such representations have been argued to foster prejudice, intolerance, and hatred (McGarry 2017). The Roma have historically experienced extreme levels of discrimination and racism (Breazu 2020) and are presently Europe's most marginalized ethnic group, suffering from ongoing social exclusion, extreme poverty, limited access to schooling, job markets, and proper healthcare (FRA 2020; Orton et al. 2022). These socioeconomic inequalities are absent or infrequently articulated in the media and political discourse, which often present begging or living in make-shift camps as inherent Romani cultural practices, rather than the consequences of their social exclusion (Breazu 2020; Djuve et al. 2016).

In this article we consider the case of Swedish news media, arguing that the representation of the Roma significantly diverges from the narratives commonly found in other European contexts. Scholarly work on the representation of Roma within the Swedish media, albeit limited, indicates a tendency for the Roma to be predominantly portrayed in contexts related to begging and characterized as undesirable EU citizens (Arasu, 2022; Svan, 2019). Moreover, research focusing on digital platforms reveals that Roma are frequently subjected to hate speech and discrimination on social media (Enarsson and Lindgren, 2019). In our analysis, we leverage a selection of articles from Swedish national newspapers and our findings show that there is not the same negative construction of Roma as backward, criminal, and threatening that are commonly seen in various European media. Yet, informed by scholarly discussions on Swedish racism and the notion of 'Swedish exceptionalism,' our detailed Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis (MCDA) of eight news reports—part of a larger dataset—reveals a prevalent use of human rights discourse which serves as a form of

disclaiming racism (van Dijk 2015). Such manner of representation subtly perpetuates reactions and measures towards the Roma that mirror those found elsewhere in Europe. After the 2007 EU enlargement, Romanian and Bulgarian economic migrants, including ethnic Roma became increasingly attracted to Nordic countries due to their economic opportunities and welfare systems (Hansson & Mitchell 2018; Wigerfelt & Wigerfelt 2015). Among these, Roma with less schooling and limited language skills were unable to find work or accommodation (Barker 2017). These migrants lived in improvised settlements and earned a living from begging or busking in various Swedish municipalities. For the Swedish public the widespread visibility of Roma, begging in major squares, bus stops, subways, and in front of supermarkets, was experienced as something disturbing and unsettling (Barker 2017; Hansson & Mitchell 2018). On the one hand, in Sweden, there have been debates on the impact of begging on public order and safety. On the other hand, there were concerns about the wellbeing of those who beg. Anti-immigration sentiments, including Romaphobia in Sweden and other contexts intensified, especially after the 2015 refugee crises (Breazu & McGarry 2023; Ekström et al 2023; Krzyżanowski 2020), when Sweden experienced a rise in far-right politics and Roma migrants became victims of violence from extremist groups (*The Irish Times* 2019).

In 2016, the extreme right-wing Sweden Democrat Party (Sverigedemokraterna) introduced a campaign to remove Roma beggars from the streets with the aim of returning them to their Eastern European countries (Barker 2017; Bolton 2015). Surveys have shown that this resonated with concerns of the majority of the population (Barker 2017). On that basis, as European nationals, not formerly registered in Sweden, it was decided that the Roma had no legal right to claim any form of welfare (Hansson & Mitchell 2018). The government also explored some largely unsuccessful initiatives to work with the Romanian and Bulgarian authorities to provide opportunities for Roma to remain in their home countries. In the Romanian news media, these were represented as simple attempts at expulsion from Sweden (Adevarul 2015), similar to measures undertaken by other European countries that were highly criticized by human rights organizations (Amnesty International 2018; Breazu & Machin 2018).

In this article, we begin by considering the research literature on racism in Sweden, where, due to its history and post-war socio-political developments, a number of discourses tend to block or distort open discussions of issues related to race and social inequalities. We then conduct a close analysis of eight articles from two Swedish newspapers (*Aftonbladet* and *Dagens Nyheter*) to examine how Roma migrants in Sweden are represented as part of the 2016 debates on the ban on begging.

Racism, inequality and White Swedishness

Overall, Nordic countries have been regarded and have presented themselves as fundamentally non-racist, open, equal, fair and rational societies (Hübinette & Lundström 2014). In particular, Sweden has had an international reputation as a model of tolerance, human rights and social equality (Schierup & Ålund 2011). This emerged as the Swedish government became vocal in the 1960s and 70s about issues of oppression and injustice, notably with regards to the American war in Vietnam, the apartheid in South Africa and more broadly speaking out in favour of decolonisation (Hübinette & Lundström 2011). Sweden has historically been credited as having the highest number of refugees per capita compared to other European countries (Jahan 2016). With its social democratic system and strong welfare state, oriented toward the fundamental reduction of social and economic inequalities, along with progress in gender equality, Sweden appeared to be the modern Western society

model: rational, just and fair (Hübinette & Lundström 2014)—something that has been part of the national self-image and Sweden's nation branding (Hübinette & Lundström 2011). In Swedish school materials, it is overtly stated that Sweden leads the world in freedom, democracy, and rights (Danielsson Malmros 2012).

In Sweden itself, there is a culture and policy of 'color-blindness' (Bonilla-Silva 2013; Mulinari & Neergaard 2017), where it is held that all people are to be treated equally and where racism is believed to be largely absent from society, with the exception of a small minority of far-right extremist groups (Hübinette & Arbouz 2019). Color-blindness is a term used in critical race studies to account for an ideology where it is assumed that being non-racist, or anti-racist, is not to see race as a relevant category since all people are viewed as equal (Bonilla-Silva 2013). This approach often involves opposing racial categorization itself as a means to combat racism (Goldberg 2009). Starting in 1996, the Swedish government has tried to eliminate the term 'race' from all public documents (Atak 2022; Osanami Törngren 2022), and today it has become a word to be avoided in everyday life. There is a widespread belief in Sweden that access to various societal sectors, including employment and education, does not discriminate based on race (Rakar 2010; Schierup & Ålund 2010). Furthermore, many Swedish people consider 'race' as an insignificant factor in discussions about discrimination or social inequalities (Hübinette et al. 2012; Mulinari & Neergaard 2017). This perspective is reinforced by the belief in universal human rights and the existence of legal frameworks which prevent racism to manifest.

In fact, both the internal and international views of Sweden appear to be outdated and misrepresent its ideology with regard to race. These are important to our understanding of how Roma are represented in the Swedish news media. On the one hand, Sweden has undergone massive changes since the 1990s, in particular as neoliberal political and economic principles have seen its welfare system transformed and dismantled, resulting in higher social and economic inequalities (Mulinari & Neergaard 2010). There has been a shift to privatization and outsourcing of services across all social services (Vogel 2000). International reports show that socioeconomic inequalities in Sweden are the fastest growing among OECD countries (OECD 2017), specifically with the highest increases in relation to children (UNICEF 2016).

On the other hand, Sweden also records growing inequalities in relation to race. The major Swedish cities have become some of Europe's most segregated in terms of race, where White Swedes dominate more affluent areas, and ethnic minorities, mainly from Africa and the Middle East, are grouped into poorer run-down areas (Östh et al. 2015; Sernhede, Rosales & Söderman 2019). The life opportunities and access to resources of these people from ethnic minorities are also very different from those of White Swedes, with regard to the job market (Alatalo & Ostapenko 2014), schooling (Brandén & Bygren 2022), and the social stigma that comes from living in such areas (Vallström 2015). Studies have shown that members of ethnic minorities often experience discrimination and report that 'whiteness' matters in contemporary Sweden, as their skin colour prevents them from being seen as Swedish in the same way as White Swedes (Kalonaityte et al. 2008; Sawyer 2002; Yngvesson 2015). As Hübinette and Arbouz (2019) argue, while there is a refusal to talk about or recognize race in Sweden, the structural and discursive elements of racism are clearly present.

The prevailing notion of Sweden as a society devoid of racism is subject to critical scrutiny. This perception is contentious due to what scholars have observed as a whitewashing of Sweden's pre-WWII history, which silences a specific legacy that informs contemporary

policies of colour-blindness (Hübinette & Arbouz 2019; Hübinette & Lundström 2014). It was after the WWII when Sweden started to disassociate from its racist history, as Swedish leaders began to speak out in favour of decolonization and align with human rights issues. It was declared that Sweden was free of the kind of historical baggage of colonialism and race ideology, which characterized other European societies (McEachrane 2018).

In fact, while not having colonies on the same scale as other European countries, Sweden fully participated in and benefitted from that system (McEachrane 2018). This included the material benefit, access to resources and the trade structures produced by global colonialism (Antoine 2022). It also included ideas centred on the superiority of white European race and inferiority of those of non-Germanic origins (Kotljarchuk 2020). Here culture and biology were conflated where Europeans were intelligent, civilized, rational and sophisticated in contrast to the primitive and savage peoples they conquered, used as resources and sought to educate and enlighten (Palmberg 2009). Not only did Sweden embrace such views on racial order, but it was also a leader of the European eugenic movement, seeing itself as 'whiteness deluxe'—a concept embodying a sense of racial superiority—becoming a world leader in the study and knowledge production of scientific racism (Hübinette & Lundström 2014, 430). The Swedes had seen themselves as most white of whites and as such a kind of human elite (Hagerman 2006).

In the 1900s until WWII, in a project of nation building, eugenics-based laws were introduced to protect the notion of Swedish purity (Hübinette & Lundström 2014). Among others, these discouraged marriage with disabled people or with races of non-Germanic origins, such as Sami or Roma, a program of sterilization in the lower social classes (Antoine 2022; Kotljarchuk 2020), as well as instituting such ideas within the schooling system (Johannisson 1991). Sterilization ran until 1975, being the largest such program to exist in Europe and it particularly targeted Roma and travellers (Tydén 2000).

It has been contended that this notion of 'white deluxe' was then carried forward in the thinking of the post WWII Sweden and into the era of human rights promotion (Hübinette & Lundström 2014). While scientific racism had been rejected, Sweden with its cultural baggage and identity still being formed in a largely homogenous society, now based on equality and human rights, was the best example of White societies defined by openness, progressiveness and modern rationality (Hübinette & Lundström 2014). This view of Sweden became imprinted in new sense of nation building, with Nordic Whiteness at its core, forming an almost 'cultural and spiritual complement to social democracy' (Facos 1998, 3). For Hübinette and Lundström (2014, 427) whiteness and purity were a fundamental part of Swedish nationalism in the 'golden age' of the Social Democratic era. Whiteness linked the pre-WWII nationalism with the new democratic, equal and humanistic Sweden (Björck 2000; Dahlqvist 2002). A new form of homogenization under what was called *Folkhemmet*, usually translated as 'People's Home', but with connotations of 'Race Home' (Hübinette & Lundström 2014) took place, driving the notion of equality in the new Sweden, but which produced an ideology of integration and exclusion in particular affecting the Swedish Sami population and Roma (Catomeris 2004).

While other European countries such as France, Nederland and the UK had become richly multicultural by the 1980s, particularly through arrivals from their former colonies, Sweden was still a highly homogenous country, with smaller numbers of minority groups and refugees coming from outside Europe, such as Chile in the 1970s and Somalia and Syria in the 1980s (Osanami Törngren et al. 2018). However, after the 2015 refugee crisis, Sweden,

with its population of around 10 million become one of the world's most super-diverse nations in a short span of time (Hübinette & Arbouz 2019). This rapid shift has also made Sweden one of the world's most racially segregated societies.

Critics have argued that Sweden's policy of colour-blindness creates problems. This is because race has never been discussed as a factor in relation to social or political issues (Hübinette & Lundström 2014), which makes it difficult to talk about institutionalized racism or racial discrimination. In addition, the policy of colour-blindness, along with the discourse of Swedish exceptionalism, formed in a highly homogenous society, contributed to very low levels of racial literacy among the Swedish public, implying that racial issues can be addressed in superficial, naive, or clumsy ways. This provides the context for the analysis of the representation of Roma, the introduction of the anti-begging laws, and the calls for repatriations to Eastern Europe in the Swedish press.

Theory and Method

The analysis in this article draws on Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis (MCDA) (Machin & Mayr 2023), which is part of the broader tradition of Critical Discourse Studies (CDS), where interest lies in the role of language and communication in the functioning of social and political life (Flowerdew & Richardson 2017). Drawing on a Foucauldian (2013) understanding, 'discourse' refers to social models through which people account for the nature of things in the world. Such discourses tend to be ideological, especially since they reproduce the ideas and interests of dominant groups in a society. As Foucault argues, discourses lie not only in language use but also in shaping processes and activities in our societies. They inform how things are done and why, what priorities we hold, how we plan and build our institutions, and how we judge what and who is good or bad (Fairclough 2013). In CDA, the analyst conducts a close analysis of instances of communication to reveal the discourses buried in texts that may be less obvious to the casual reader. In MCDA, the analyst also pays attention to the visual aspect of communication, such as news photography, graphs, charts or other visual elements in news reports.

In MCDA, data can be approached to draw out what Van Leeuwen (2008) calls 'discursive scripts'. This involves identifying the 'elements' that comprise a discourse, such as participants, actions, performance modes, causalities evaluations, time and place, and resources. For Van Leeuwen (2008), such a process is highly productive since we can reveal how these scripts are different from, or recontextualize, the actual events or situations they are used to represent. For example, we can ask if in a discursive script, elements such as participants, actions, or settings are left out, somehow modified, or if new elements have been added. For Fairclough (2013), we can reveal the ideological qualities of representations in news texts, for example, by asking where representational strategies mean that the identities of participants are not clear, or where events, processes and actions take the form of abstractions rather than clear transparent accounts.

In this article we focus on the discourses carried by Swedish newspapers in 2016. This period was chosen for three reasons. First, it followed the 2015 European refugee crisis, when anti-immigrant sentiment in Sweden increased in intensity, with racism and xenophobia extending beyond refugees to other groups, such as Muslims, the Roma, and other Eastern European migrants (Ekman 2018; Krzyżanowski 2018; Wernesjö 2020). Second, this is a time when the widespread general frustration with the presence of Eastern European Roma beggars was instrumentalized by right-wing politicians to consolidate their positions prior to elections (Hansson & Mitchell 2018). Third, 2016 was marked by public debates regarding

criminalizing begging in Sweden (Barker 2017). Data were collected from the Svenska Dagstidningar database, searching the four leading Swedish newspapers for items reporting on the Roma, begging and EU migrants: *Aftonbladet* (79), *Dagens Nyheter* (299), *Expressen* (254) and *Svenska Dagbladet* (86). Translations were carried out by the authors and checked by a Swedish native speaker.

In this article, we wanted to capture how the discourse is framed in two different newspapers with different styles of journalism and which have slightly different readership. DN is one of Sweden's leading morning newspapers with a broad readership that targets urban liberal professionals, often being considered a mainstream newspaper with a more 'serious' tone. *Aftonbladet* is left-leaning tabloid and reaches a different demographic, often focusing on sensational and popular news. We have identified key issues/events which were covered by both newspapers and which shaped the public discourse about Roma migrants and criminalizing begging in Sweden. First, we conducted a semantic macro-structure analysis (van Dijk, 2009) to map out the themes used to represent Roma across our sample. Then we carried out an MCDA analysis on a set of texts which best allows us to reveal the nature of these themes. While the analysis will draw out some of the differences between the two newspapers, we show that the basic underlying discursive script is of the same nature.

The analysis in this article includes four major stories covered by both *Aftonbladet* and *Dagens Nyheter*, stories covering key events in relation to the 2016 debates on criminalizing begging. The stories are as follows:

Story 1 (2 February 2016). The two newspapers report on a government press conference where an appointed 'investigator' has recommended firmer action by police against begging and illegal settlements and that EU migrants must seek support in their own countries, since they are not legally Swedish citizens.

Story 2 (20 April 2016). Transport minister has announced that existing transport rules are to be used to stop begging on public transport system property.

Story 3 (19 August 2016) Minister attends political summit in Iceland for Nordic countries where the issue of begging is one item to be discussed to explore the possibility of a begging ban.

Story 4 (31 October 2016) One of the newspapers (DN) has carried out a survey which reveals attitudes to begging in Sweden have hardened. Both titles report on this. DN also provide a vox pop type set of interviews.

To draw out the discursive script carried by the stories, the analysis begins by considering how Roma are represented. We then move on to how the 'problem' is represented, and finally to the Swedish response. We show patterns of abstractions and obfuscations in relation to how identities, actions, and causalities are represented.

How the Roma are represented

One task of CDA is to reveal specific discursive scripts used to represent people and events, paying close attention to the linguistic or visual choices used to represent participants and their actions (Fairclough 2013). Representational strategies can individualize or personalize a participant so that a reader might be encouraged to see them as an actual person under specific circumstances. People can also be anonymized or represented as generic categories or 'types of people,' that distance them from the reader. Anonymization can also be discursively realized by 'functionalization,' when people are represented in terms of what they do [beggars, illegal settlers, etc.] or in relation to one specific action (Van Leeuwen

2008). We used these ideas to draw out themes or patterns of representation of Roma in the two newspapers.

Across our sample the term 'Roma' is seldom used. It is substituted with generic terms, as illustrated in the following extracts from news reports on the Iceland summit:

Extract 1 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016):

Both Denmark and Norway have limited the beggar's opportunities.

Extract 2 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016)

Ardalan Shekarabim emphasizes that 'Sweden has more projects underway in the beggars home countries.'

Extract 3 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

Both Denmark and Norway have introduced restrictions for beggars.

Extract 4 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

The goal must be to eliminate begging.

The main representation of the Roma in *Aftonbladet* and *Dagens Nyheter* was as 'beggars'. This generic representation makes no reference to ethnicity or other circumstances. As evident in extract 1-4, the action 'begging' is used to metonymically represent Roma migrants in Sweden. On the one hand, this absence of personalization or categorization can be understood in the context of contemporary Swedish colour-blind discourse, where any mention of race and ethnicity is viewed as problematic and irrelevant (Mulinari & Neegaard 2017; Osanami Törngren 2022). On the other hand, this representation of 'beggars' and 'begging' means that Roma migrants are largely reduced to this action alone. The reporting is not about a historically marginalized group struggling to survive, but about 'beggars' and 'begging'. The backgrounding or omission of details about the identities of the people carrying out the begging is one way of recontextualizing the nature of the actual situation, to use Van Leeuwen's (2008) term.

In the reports, we also find other generic groupings, for example, in articles that call for tougher policing:

Extract 5 (Aftonbladet 2 February 2016)

Police need to get better at stopping EU migrant's illegal settlements.

Extract 6 (Aftonbladet 2 February 2016)

I do not think we should encourage this group to bring their children to Sweden if one cannot secure a good enough housing situation. [says, Martin Valdfridsson]

Extract 7 (Dagens Nyheter 2 February 2016)

On behalf of the government, Valdfridsson has investigated how society should deal with vulnerable EU citizens who are in Sweden.

Extract 8 (Dagens Nyheter 2 February 2016)

The police must use the laws that are already in place to evict people who have settled illegally.

In both newspapers, Roma migrants are represented generically as 'EU migrants' [EU-migranter] and 'EU citizens' [EU-medborgare], as illustrated in Extracts 5 and 7. Again, in

the color-blind discourse, 'illegal settlements' and bringing children to Sweden cannot be tied to Roma overtly. These generic terms also communicate a sense of unbelonging, implying that they belong elsewhere. Specifically, this relates to the Swedish government regulation according to which EU migrants, not formally registered in the Swedish welfare system and without a Swedish personal number, do not qualify for any welfare support (Barker 2017) and should therefore return to their home countries.

In extract 8, *Dagens Nyheter* makes reference to 'people who have settled illegally' [manniskor som bosatt sig illegalt]. The use of the term 'illegal' is an important addition to this discursive script. The coined term 'illegal settlements' covers up that such actions are driven by poverty, desperation and lack of resources to find alternative accommodation from within the system. The term 'people' suggests a sense of objectivity and neutrality, suggesting that this is about *any* person who might carry out such an act rather than specifically targeting Roma migrants. The same representational strategy is evident in extract 6 where 'this group' is mentioned, but not specifically named. In such reports, given the public profile of these events, it is unlikely that readers will not understand to whom 'this group' refers, just as they will understand that the term 'people' is glossing over who may actually be targeted for evictions. As begging becomes a metonym for the whole situation, 'illegal settlements', become the target of eviction rather than the people living in them (Breazu & Machin 2018).

The reports about the implementation of stricter transport rules refer to Roma, yet they are not directly linked to problematic behavior:

Extract 9 (Aftonbladet 20 April 2016)

Among other things no one is allowed to sit on the floor, and it is forbidden to disturb others.

Extract 10 (Aftonbladet 20 April 2016)

This is nothing that is aimed at a specific set of events or group, but rather general review of the regulations in public transport.

Extract 11 (Dagens Nyheter 20 April 2016)

SL must also evict illegal settlements in areas close to public transport. (...)

Extract 12 (Dagens Nyheter 20 April 2016)

'We do not think these are bad people. They do not want to create insecurity. They want to follow laws and regulations but have no knowledge of what applies. Therefore, we will try to teach non-profit organizations that have contact with Roma.'

In extract 9 from *Aftonbladet*, there is a sense that the new transport rules do not specifically target the Roma migrants, since the communication is impersonalized: 'no one is allowed to sit on the floor' [ska ingen får sitta på golvet] 'it is forbidden to disturb others' [det är förbjudet att störa andra]. The use of indefinite pronouns (no one, others) implies that these rules apply to everyone, and therefore, they are not discriminatory in any way. At times, as exemplified in extract 10 from *Dagens Nyheter*, there are disclaimers which overtly state that no specific group is being singled out. In Extract 11, mention of the Roma are substituted by 'illegal settlements.'

Even though Roma are mentioned in extract 11, it is never overtly stated that it is they who are begging or settling illegally. Such a direct mention of the Roma is preceded by a disclaimer: 'We do not think these are bad people.' The 'problem' is explained, not in relation

to the Roma's long history with social exclusion and harsh poverty, but to their purported lack of culturally specific knowledge.

The visual representation of those begging also contributes to how the discourse about Roma migrants is constructed. Here we find one of the main differences in representation between the two newspapers. Visually, we can also examine the extent to which participants are represented in ways that individualize them, anonymize them, depict them as generic types, or conflate them with single actions (Machin and Mayr, 2023).

Aftonbladet shows scenes that point to the clash of cultures, disorder, and changes in Swedish society caused by Roma's migration. This affront to everyday Swedish city life is not represented in written texts. The news photographs in *Aftonbladet* (Figures 1 and 2) depict bleak scenes of the clutter of bedding and belongings, and forlorn people begging among passing shoppers. In Figure 1, the photograph carries a caption: 'ONE CAN GO TO PRISON: In Denmark, there is a national ban on begging and in Norway municipalities have the right to reinforce local bans.' Therefore, the caption frames the scene as a legal offence that may require extreme forms of punishment. Such images can serve to anchor and give meaning to matters that are more vaguely formulated in the text (Machin & Mayr 2023).

Dagens Nyheter employs imagery that tends to gloss over the vivid suffering and trauma experienced by individuals living in profound marginalization and poverty. A notable characteristic of these images, exemplified in Figure 2, is their portrayal from what appears to be the beggar's viewpoint: a hand extended forward with a backdrop of indistinct passersby. Such a perspective seems to place the reader in the shoes of a Roma individual; however, the complexity and reality of the Roma's situation are obscured. They are depicted merely in the act of begging, with the true context of their lives made indistinct and depersonalized, reduced to a symbol of an outstretched hand against the vague bustle of a shopping street. This portrayal, which strips away the Roma's agency and frames them as inherently vulnerable, has been cited as reflective of Swedish official policy. Such policy narratives perpetuate the perception of the Roma as unemployable, contributors of little societal value, and present them as a problem in need of resolution (Alexiadou and Norberg, 2017; Helakorpi et al., 2018).

In the survey articles (Figures 5), while *Aftonbladet* presents an unsettling scene encountered by shoppers (an elderly woman and a disabled man begging in a main city square), *Dagens Nyheter* provides polished close-up photographs of two women who beg. They are named and described as mothers who seek money to feed their children. In a sense, this does not foreground wider circumstances in which the Roma exist and survive, but rather a single motivation that makes those begging 'more like us', with relatable parental concerns. Later discussions reveal that this portrayal adopts a humanitarian lens, albeit one that lacks depth and fails to engage with the complexities of the Roma's plight. It even neglects the shifting public opinion in Sweden, where a growing proportion of the people is increasingly averse to begging in their communities. Such representations are symptomatic of the limited racial awareness among Sweden's white middle class (Antoine, 2022; Osanami Törngren, 2022), who still hold onto the myth of Swedish exceptionalism.

Figure 5. Photograph from *Aftonbladet* survey article

The ‘Problem’ of begging

In this section we examine how the two newspapers represent the nature of the 'problem' of begging. In MCDA research, an important part of the discursive script is to identify how problems, causalities, and solutions are represented (Breazu 2020; Machin & Mayr 2023). This is done by examining instances where arguments are not clearly formulated, where causalities lack clarity, or are represented by means of abstractions and presuppositions where undefined or contestable issues are presented as given and widely agreed upon (Fairclough 2013). Both *Aftonbladet* and *Dagens Nyheter* were reluctant to name the Roma as the targeted group associated with the 'problem' they refer to as 'begging.' Notably in both newspapers the reason why a prohibition on begging is necessary remains ambiguous.

The problem is always at the core represented as 'begging.' Begging is used as a framing device for stories. For example, in survey articles:

Extract 13 (*Aftonbladet* 31 October 2016)
Should begging be banned?

Extract 14 (*Dagens Nyheter* 31 October 2016)
More and more Stockholmers want to see a ban on begging.

However, when we look across the stories, it is never explicit as to why begging should be banned.

In the coverage of the Iceland meeting, we found the following:

Extract 15 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016)

We cannot pass the responsibility for the problem to the Swedish municipalities.

Extract 16 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016)

Both Denmark and Norway have limited the beggars' opportunities.

Extract 17 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

The government is considering introducing a ban on begging in Sweden, and the minister for public administration, Ardalan Shekarabi, intends to study the models that exist in our Nordic neighbouring countries.

Extract 18 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

It is natural that we learn from the experiences of other countries, he [Ardalan Shekarabi] says.

These reports highlight 'the problem' of begging and propose a 'potential solution' in the form of legislative action to prohibit it. However, neither newspaper offers concrete arguments as to why these actions are necessary. There is an intention expressed by Sweden to 'examine various models' and 'learn from the experiences' from other nations. Within this discourse, 'the problem'—though vaguely defined—and the perceived need for a solution become legitimized by the mere fact of recognition and response in other countries. As illustrated in Extract 17 from Dagens Nyheter, these actions are not attributed to specific governmental decisions or political ideology but are instead personalized as collective actions representative of the country as a whole.

In Figure 1, the photograph of an anonymized beggar from *Aftonbladet* is accompanied by a caption: 'ONE CAN GO TO PRISON.' This suggests that begging could be criminalized; however, there is no explanation as to why these harsh measures are needed. Across our analyzed sample in both *Aftonbladet* and *Dagens Nyheter*, 'begging' and 'the problem' are used as metonyms to replace the more concrete and specific accounts of the nature of the problem. Furthermore, the discourse of equality, openness and progressiveness, along with the suppression of race, provides one explanation for why the visibility of such poverty, clashing with cultural expectations, becomes difficult to discuss openly.

In both newspapers, the stories about changes in transport rules carry a list of behaviors to be prevented. This is of particular interest as it remains unclear why begging per se should be the primary target of legal action:

Extract 19 (Aftonbladet 20 April 2016)

No one is allowed to sit in the floor, and it is forbidden to disturb others.

Extract 20 (Aftonbladet 20 April 2016)

'Lying down in seating or lying or sitting on the floor, playing music without SL's written permission and otherwise behaving in a disruptive way' [says, Kristofer Tamsons]

Extract 21 (Dagens Nyheter 20 April 2016)

Just as it will be forbidden to harass or disturb people, bring bulky objects that interfere with security of leaving belongings unattended.

Extract 22 (Dagens Nyheter 20 April 2016)

The prevalence of begging has completely exploded in recent years. It is a rapidly growing source of insecurity among travelers and one of the most common complaints.

The ‘problematic behaviour’ for prohibition includes activities such as 'lying or sitting on the ground' [‘ligga ner i sittmöbler eller att ligga eller sitta på golvet’], 'playing music without the transit authority SL's explicit written consent' [‘spela musik utan SL:s skriftliga tillstånd’], 'intimidating or disturbing others' [‘ofreda annan person eller uppträda störande’], 'carrying large items that could compromise safety' [‘ta med skrymmande baggage som kan medföra fara för säkerheten’], and 'leaving personal items unattended' [‘lämna bagage utan uppsikt’]. In Dagens Nyheter, begging is specifically depicted as 'a significantly increasing source of discomfort for commuters' [‘en kraftigt växande källa till otrygghet bland resenärerna’]. However, the terms 'discomfort,' 'intimidate,' and 'disturb' remain ill-defined. The texts do not clarify whether begging would be deemed acceptable should it not engender feelings of 'discomfort.' There is a conspicuous avoidance by both newspapers to explicitly identify the Roma or to articulate the specific nature of the 'problem' as it is perceived by the Swedish people and the government.

In articles about the need for tougher police action, we found indications of other parts of the problem as represented in the discursive script:

Extract 23 (Aftonbladet 2 February 2016)

The moderates' spokesperson on the issue, Beatrice Ask, wants the government to quickly come up with proposals that make it easier to evict illegal settlements.

Extract 24 (Dagens Nyheter 2 February 2016)

The police must use the laws that are already in place to evict people who have settled illegally.

In Extracts 23 and 24 the issue of illegal settlements is raised without being linked to any specific group of people. Across these articles a collection of issues, including ‘sitting on the floor’, ‘creating insecurity for travelers’ and ‘illegal settlements’, are raised but never connected or in a clear sequence of identified agents and causalities. These appear as an unconnected cluster of issues that are then addressed through the metonym of begging and never clearly and directly in relation to the Roma.

The solution and the Swedish way

We now focus on the nature of the solutions in the discursive script. As shown above, the decision of the Swedish government, also supported by public opinion, was to send Roma migrants back to Romania and Bulgaria, making deals with the authorities in their villages—similar repatriation strategies undertaken governments in other European countries that received criticism from human rights organizations (Breazu & Machin 2018).

In the Iceland stories we find a notable twist in the logic of why begging should be banned:

Extract 25 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016)

Our starting point is that begging is not a solution to exclusion, discrimination and poverty.

Extract 26 (Aftonbladet 19 August 2016)

Ardalan Shekarabi emphasizes that Sweden has more projects underway in the beggars' home countries.

Extract 27 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

The solution to discrimination and exclusion in Romania and Bulgaria is not and will never be that we have begging on Swedish streets, says Ardalan Shekarabi.

Extract 28 (Dagens Nyheter 19 August 2016)

Ardalan Shekarabi emphasizes that Sweden has put a lot of energy into dialogue with the countries concerned and that several important projects are underway.

In Extracts 25 and 27, the representation of begging by both newspapers implies an underlying assumption that 'begging is not a solution to social exclusion, discrimination, and poverty' ['tiggeri inte är en lösning på utanförskap, diskriminering och fattigdom']. Here a position is taken as if challenging that misconception. There is an insinuation that the Swedish government is seeking the *actual* solution, as indicated in Extracts 26 and 28, which reference unspecified 'projects' in the beggars' home countries where Sweden has put 'a lot of energy into dialogue' [Sverige har lagt mycket energi på att ha dialog med de berörda länderna och att flera viktiga projekt är igång]. This suggests that Sweden does not simply wish to be rid of the Roma but to actively seek real remedies to poverty which are consistent with Sweden's commitment to human rights and the dignity of all individuals.

Solutions relating to tougher policing or bringing about a legal ban on begging are also presented with an emphasis on human rights considerations. In Extract 10, Aftonbladet stresses that the revisions to public transport regulations were 'not aimed at a specific set of events or particular group' [det här är ingenting som är riktat mot en speciell företeelse eller en speciell grupp]. In *Dagens Nyheter* we find a similar discourse:

Extract 29 (Dagens Nyheter 2 February 2016)

...the county administrations' responsibility for coordination is important so that everyone is treated equally.

Here the 'coordination' in fact relates to begging restrictions, yet it is the issues of 'equality' (everyone is treated equally) that is emphasized.

In stories about tougher policing, concerns about the welfare of Roma children are raised:

Extract 30 (Aftonbladet 2 February 2016).

'I do not think that we should encourage this group to bring their children to Sweden if one cannot secure a good enough housing situation' (says Valfridsson) 'new problems arise, slum communities, which we frantically worked to get rid of.'

Extract 31 (Dagens Nyheter 2 February 2016).

Valfridsson points out that begging often leads to families being split up by parents leaving their children in their home country while they come to Sweden and beg.

In these extracts, the prohibition on begging is represented as partly motivated by the welfare of Roma children, either in relation to homelessness or the potential neglect that may occur while parents are in Sweden. It is never stated 'begging must be banned to protect Roma children.' Signified here is that the underlying concern is rooted in the protection of human rights.

Extract 30 alludes to the former era of social democracy in Sweden, when concerted efforts were made to eliminate slum communities: 'new problems arise, slum communities, which we frantically worked to get rid of' [Da uppstar nya problem, slumsamhallen som vi frenetiskt arbetat for att fa bort]. Despite Sweden experiencing some of the most rapid increases in social inequality among OECD nations (OECD, 2017), this narrative harks back to the social democratic ideal of the 'Folkhemmet,' which, though now largely dismantled and romanticized, is invoked as if the specter of poverty had been decisively conquered. Within this narrative, the Roma appear to be a potential catalyst for the reemergence of such social issues. Neither newspaper presents any counter to this view.

Within the news stories, there are explicit references to international human rights legislation that serve to legitimate the need to eradicate begging. These references are particularly evident in discussions surrounding intensified policing and the implementation of new transportation regulations.

Extract 32 (Aftonbladet 20 April 2016)

According to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, children have the right to go to school, and as the investigator points out, children have been outside the school system year after year.

Extract 33 (Aftonbladet 2 February 2016)

'It is important to protect the right to freedom of movement in the EU, but those who come to Sweden should know which legislation applies,' said Asa Regner at the press conference today.

In Extract 32 from Aftonbladet, there is an implicit argument that the prohibition of begging aligns with the principles of the Convention on the Rights of the Child. In Extract 33, toughening of rules presented in the story are represented after a disclaimer, which emphasizes the importance of protecting the right to freedom of movement in the EU. The notion of 'those who come to Sweden should know which legislation applies' [den som kommer till Sverige ska veta vilken lagstiftning som galler] also carries a sense of color-blind equality where all should expect the same treatment and act in relation to social expectations in the same way.

In the *Dagens Nyheter* survey (Figure 4), we find vox pops, where cheerful white Stockholmers are named and humanized by introducing their baby or dog. Apart from one who suggests it would be better if the beggars did not come, the other responses are emblematic of a color-blind humanitarian approach. For example:

Extract 34 (Dagens Nyheter 31 October 2016)

I don't think a ban is the right way to go. It affects so many people.

Although the survey results indicate a mere 16% of Swedes are in open support of begging, the report by Dagens Nyheter portrays a narrative of compassion. Here, Swedish exceptionalism, combined with color-blindness and limited racism literacy is marked. Without wishing to criticize the sentiments expressed, the shifts in Swedish society and the very specific situation of the Roma were erased.

In the *Aftonbladet* story about the survey it is noted that

Extract 35 (Aftonbladet 31 October 2016)

The strongest support for an outright ban is found among men, the middle aged, in Central Sweden and SD voters.

Here, again, there is a shift away from the reality of what the figures broadly show. In this case, as has been observed, racism and the exclusion of Roma are seen as un-Swedish, as exceptions, typically located in specific groups away from the key urban centers (HübINETTE & ARBOUZ 2019).

Conclusion

At a surface level the news reports in the Swedish press are different from those observed in other European news media regarding the representation of Roma. The analysed news reports do not carry the same overt and direct prejudice or hatred towards the Roma. However, the analysis reveals a discursive script in which the presence of the Roma is clearly problematic. Yet there is an avoidance of clearly stating this. A number of Critical Discourse Analysts, such as Fairclough (2013) and van Leeuwen (2008), have argued that the lack of clarity, obfuscation or suppression of important information in any instance of communication, are clear indicators of an underlying ideological tension. While our analysis identified certain differences between the two newspapers, the underlying discursive script is the same.

The Swedish government's decision to deny the Roma any kind of welfare support and repatriate them to Eastern Europe received similar criticism to that of earlier measure by other European governments (Amnesty International 2018; Breazu & Machin 2018). This Swedish policy was clearly supported and driven by national opinion polls, which showed that public attitudes towards 'begging' had become less tolerant especially after the 2015 refugee crisis (Hansson & Mitchell 2018). For some observers, such sentiments were part of the political shifts in Sweden, with a broader rise of racist and anti-migrant views (Ekman 2018; Ekström et al. 2023; Krzyżanowski 2018). However, in these news reports, such shifts, along with broader changes in Swedish society were excluded.

The ideological conflict evident here may be interpreted through the lens of the myth of Swedish exceptionalism, which emerged within a historically homogenous society and is now challenged by the stark visibility of profound racial and socioeconomic disparities in public spaces. A closer analysis of these news stories reveals that Sweden's self-perception as an inherently non-racist society hinders open discussions about what is taking place. It also shows how the Swedish discourse of tolerance, human rights and social equality also becomes a kind of disclaimer for the very attitudes and actions criticized by human rights organizations.

For Eastern European Roma migrants, the Swedish press may not play a role in openly fostering social exclusion as observed in other European contexts. Nonetheless, the result is

the same. The situation of Roma migrants living in poverty or suffering from social exclusion is not represented as an European humanitarian issue, but as a problem to be solved, which in practice means finding 'legal ways' to return Roma back to their countries of origins, leaving their situation unchanged.

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